

Developing an Applicable Design for Cylindrical Non-Contact Triboelectric Nanogenerators to Harvest Hydraulic Energy for Sensing and Detection

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Abstract - Triboelectric nanogenerators (TENGs) can maintain constant operation in hydraulic systems, even in remote locations. Electrostatic induction drives the triboelectric effect to redistribute a material's electric charge by the influence of nearby charges that pulls loose electrons in one direction, forming a current that powers the triboelectric effect.

Advancements in technology that allows contemporary sensors to be made far more compact than their predecessors, and with a greater need for self-sustaining off-grid sensors, small-scale energy production can provide the necessary power without overshooting the power requirement. Furthermore, unlike a battery TENGs do not need to be replaced.

The current design averaged at 248.57 mV and 0.35 mA respectively. As all the energy came from flowing water, a renewable power source, and it does not lose voltage over time, triboelectric nanogenerators could provide opportunities for detection that could be integrated into hard-to-reach hydraulic infrastructure.

Index Terms – Electrostatic induction, hydraulic energy, non-contact, triboelectric nanogenerator

INTRODUCTION

Advancements in technology continue to constantly allow for contemporary sensors that are made far more compact than their predecessors. Due to the correlation between overall size and the voltage required for the device to properly function, many end up overshooting the voltage needed, leading to extra electricity wasted. To remedy this, large-scale factories invest in voltage optimization equipment, which in turn saves them money. For the increasingly common small-scale gadgets, the same voltage optimization equipment is considered impractical; on the large scale, this leads to wasted electricity, which has been shown to be as much as 10-20%. Tying into the Internet of Things with advancement of sensor networks, the advancements in nanotechnology allow for the optimization of low-powered sensors that can remedy this issue while providing “continuous and accurate measurements” [1], where instead of batteries the sensors are powered by mechanical movement in the surrounding environment. In 2012, a team led by Zhong Lin Wang gained traction with

their triboelectric nanogenerators as “an emerging mechanical energy harvesting technology” [2]. Triboelectric nanogenerators, lending to their small size, can fit into compact devices as sensors to open doors to electronics, including those found in phones and medical sensors - they are already low-voltage, and cheap energy sources by default, and could have major implications in low-powered sensors, benefiting from an economic, technological and environmental standpoint.

1. An Alternative Micro-Energy Source from Harvesting Mechanical Movement

The triboelectric effect, which produces voltage through the contact of two opposite-charged materials, was discovered before 2600 BC. However, only until modern times has it been looked at as an alternate energy source [3]. Different materials create a stronger triboelectrification, however all contact between two materials produce to some extent a level of the triboelectric effect. Wang explains how that may be possible for new technology, such as self-powered sensors, to create new niches among electronics to reimagine small-scale power production, and possibly hold the capability to offset the current demand for energy by converting everyday mechanical energy to usable electrical energy. Like the piezoelectric effect, or static electricity, two materials with opposite electrical charges that interact with each other can create usable electricity, although the triboelectric effect has been viewed separately in more real-world application. Triboelectric nanogenerators have been primarily viewed as a micro-power source, outputting usable energy from human motion, mechanical vibrations, moving automobiles, wind, and raindrops, although there have also been considerations for macro-power sources, such as harvesting usable energy from ocean waves [4]. Primarily, application has been focused on low-power sensors in the Internet of Things that will be able to run only with the aid of mechanical energy. Considering how widespread this effect is, it opens many options to create applications for energy harvesting from mechanical movement. As of now, possible optimizations can be split into two main groups, systems and circuit designs, and materials and material designs [5]. However, now, the systems and circuit designs stand to benefit from greater optimization for the same materials that can be used differently to achieve higher voltages.

II. The Leading Mechanism Behind the Triboelectric Effect: Contact Electrification

Since the discovery of the triboelectric effect and the introduction of triboelectric nanogenerators, understanding at the microscopic level has finally been opened [2, 6]. It is now widely understood that electron transfer is the primary mechanism of contact electrification, the driving variable in power production. In essence, the movement of electrons across the surface of material(s) electrifies the surface, and with the greater the amount of surface area, the more electrons can be transferred. When the charge is sustained, and as the two materials move the electrons are pulled in a single direction, creating a current. With the discovery of new polymers and materials that aid the triboelectric effect having been stalled, recent research focuses upon how the materials are incorporated in the larger design.

III. Secondary Mechanisms that Enhance the Triboelectric Effect

Besides material aspects, other factors play a role in maximizing the voltage of triboelectric nanogenerators. Techniques that have been used to increase surface area can be seen with nanolithographic patterning [7], where the nanopatterns on metal have gotten as small as 10-100 nanometers, as well as chemical etching [8] which is the most common type of etching which aims to simply enhance nanostructures with a combination of oxidizing and reducing agents. The overarching goal between these two methods is to maximize voltage production by manipulating surface area, which is reflected in research by Nurmakanov that cites techniques like these as a source for novel research exploring different configurations of triboelectric nanogenerator design [9]. The triboelectric effect may be a given; nearly any two materials which come into contact create a charge on their surface. To supply usable energy, as in energy in high enough volumes to power a device, even potent materials cannot be used by themselves.

IV. New Research to Advance Triboelectric Nanogenerators and their Applications

Now, the recent wave of research has cast a broad net at the various shapes a triboelectric effect can take, and many specific types have been sparsely researched and left for future testing and modification. Triboelectric nanogenerators can be further split into four subcategories: contact-separation mode, sliding mode, single-electrode mode, and freestanding mode. Of these, freestanding mode is unique for having no contact between the two diodes, which prevents potential wear [6, 10-11]. This research delves into the comparison to the contact-separation mode, freestanding mode has an additional advantage in speed at which the mechanical motion can occur, increasing the threshold for power output that can be remedied to fit the final product: one capable of producing more energy. The freestanding mode represented in a free-rotating disk design can use its structural advantages to advance tribology in its application for low-powered sensors [1]. Furthermore, it has been used as a step towards

sustainable electricity in hydraulics, as it can be recreated in a cylindrical design that, being non-contact, negates any abrasion which extends the lifespan of the triboelectric nanogenerator [12]. The basic premise, more clearly described by Chung et. al, centers around meeting the requirement of voltage for smaller sensors that take ambient measurements, that can benefit from a high voltage, self-sustaining power source [13].

In this work, the triboelectric nanogenerators work through hydraulics, supplying the needed mechanical energy from regular water flow. In an expansion upon past research, it continues the switch from a contact-separation model to contact-separation. From there, the approach has shifted from a disk-shaped triboelectric nanogenerator to the superior cylindrical model, which aims to compartmentalize the components and aid in hydraulic application. The electricity production in this research will come from the non-contact interactions between the polymer FEP and Cu foil in a cylindrical design, which produces an alternating current that can be transferred to direct current using a Schottky diode. The coaxial position between the two materials allows for net electron movement that may be capable of sustaining low-powered sensors.

Overall, the aim is to expand upon development for an applicable design for cylindrical non-contact triboelectric nanogenerators to harvest hydraulic energy for sensing and detection. Furthermore, this project will test to what extent does the surface area of a cylindrical free-standing triboelectric nanogenerator harvest clean, sustainable energy for low-powered sensing. This will be done through the application of ferric chloride to leave an imprint on the Cu foil to increase overall surface area of the substrate. To expand upon the non-contact triboelectric nanogenerator design, an accessible variation of a hydraulics-based design will be designed to generate a direct current that can be harvested as renewable energy for low-powered sensors. The design itself uses flanges to spin in a circular motion that spins the outer polymer layer to transfer electrons across the substrate. When the triboelectric nanogenerator substrate has its surface area increased by the ferric chloride chemical etching, then there will be a valuable increase in output, proportional to the increase. If etching is introduced, the triboelectric nanogenerators will likely be able to power small sensors, as the way the material is used matters for voltage output. As surface area is important for the triboelectric effect, which is based on electrification of opposite materials' surfaces, the increased surface area should increase the size, as supported by previous research into this topic. Otherwise, it may not be able to power a small sensor that, while in low-sleep mode, could provide ambient sensing from its environment in exchange for small amounts of sustainable energy.

With the increase in interest for the Internet of Things, which values sensor networks and miniaturized electronics to push the frontier of technology, by these triboelectric nanogenerators acting as sustainable batteries for a wide variety of low-powered sensors, other researchers may implement them to power larger circuits. While batteries need

to be monitored, triboelectric nanogenerators do not require huge manpower or materials to provide an energy supply. Within its own niche, there has yet to exist a non-contact hydraulic design for triboelectric nanogenerators that provides direct current in any published research. Furthermore, with only one article publicly available on this specific niche of triboelectric nanogenerator, there has not been enough exploration into techniques to increase the surface area of the substrate that can be fabricated at large scales at a cheaper cost. Eventually, research into these nanogenerators may spill over to macro-scale power from waves and other movement from bodies of water, but for as it stands right now, this design looks very promising to power sensor networks with a self-sustaining current.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

I. Chemical Treatment of Cu Substrate

The modification of the Cu substrate was chemically done through a single-displacement reaction using a solution containing ferric chloride and hydrochloric acid. This aimed to remove Cu from the desired portions of the substrate by adding the chloride ions from ferric chloride to create CuCl_2 , which then is dissolved into the solution (1). The ratio for the solution was 5 mL of hydrochloric acid, and 20 mL of distilled water for every gram of ferric chloride. The etching was done under a fume hood for five minutes; the Cu substrate, along with a vinyl containing the desired pattern, was submerged into the ferric chloride solution; the result can be seen on the Cu surface of the TENG in Fig. 1(a).

II. Characterization of both the Chemically Etched and Laser Engraved Cu Substrates

The surface patterning on the chemically modified substrate was transferred from vinyl. This was cut using a Cricut machine to a desired pattern, that was then laid on top of the Cu, attaching with an adhesive. The pattern fulfilled two criteria. One of which was the continuity of the pattern to where it could be applied in one piece, allowing for easier manufacturing of the substrate. The other was the repeating but detailed structures that provided a consistent change in plane that increased the overall surface area.

The same pattern was used for laser engraving the substrate. This time, it was uploaded to a PC program. The engraving machine was set to a speed of 1000 mm/s at 100% power. The frequency used was 20 kHz. Once the laser was calibrated to 410 mm above the substrate, the process of repeating each engraving was much quicker, producing a more consistent result. Additionally, a smaller scale was possible, narrowing the pattern size from 15 cm by 15 cm to 2.5 cm by 2.5 cm.

III. TENG Design and Function

A central, nylon cylinder served as the stator that the TENG was built upon. The two triboelectric layers, the Cu

Figure 1. Design and setup for the hydraulic non-contact TENG. (a) Photograph of TENG with chemical etching. (b) Complete setup of TENG with a LabQuest3 oscilloscope and voltmeter.

substrate and FEP polymer, built off the structure. The substrate, consisting of four pieces with an area of 38 cm^2 , were attached directly with adhesive to the stator with a 3 mm gap to maintain electrical isolation from one another until the electricity flowed through the wires on one end to a central location. On the other hand, the FEP polymer, consisting of one single sheet with an area of 225 cm^2 , was held by an outer cylinder at a coaxial position, 3 mm from the Cu substrate. This served as the rotor of the TENG. The rotor spun using ball bearings, allowing it to spin the FEP polymer at approximately 100-110 rpm.

The TENG had an area stretching 15 cm that was used for the triboelectric effect, but overall was 23 cm, as 4 cm was left on either end of the stator to fit the bearings and act as a handle. The inner diameter for the Cu substrate was 41 mm, and the outer diameter for the FEP was 47 mm. Attached to the rotor, flanges were spaced 15 cm apart on the outside of the TENG to contain the water pressure it pushes five symmetrically placed blades around the TENG.

The output of the TENG was measured through a LabQuest 3 oscilloscope that, during testing, was hooked up for 30 seconds to a voltmeter, and then an ammeter, as seen in Fig. 1(b). The water flow came directly from a water faucet that allowed the rotor to reach speeds consistently averaging 100-110 rpm. The rotor also water-sealed the TENG, preventing water or humidity from affecting the environment that the Cu substrate and FEP polymer were encased in. The potential and current were measured 30 times a second to characterize the oscillations of the data and tested the output of chemical etching and laser engraving relative to no surface modifications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This TENG not only is non-contact by avoiding direct contact between Cu substrate and an FEP polymer, but hydraulic, using energy from flowing water to create renewable energy by converting it into rotational energy that spins a rotor around a stator. Before this, the FEP comes in contact once to pick up electrons from the Cu, as they have different electron affinities. Once spinning, the electrons are carried with the rotor and pick up electrons from the surface of a Cu substrate, gaining a negative charge that then passes on to another. This process, called electrostatic induction, is the driving force that causes the triboelectric effect, allowing the renewable energy to be harvested.

The effect of surface area of the Cu substrate was then investigated. As the surface area increases, there is an

Figure 2. Implementation and characterization of the laser engraved pattern on the Cu substrate. (a) The laser engraving machine transferring the pattern onto the Cu substrate. (b) The size comparison between the detailing of the engraved pattern and a standard US penny.

Figure 3. Potential and Current for TENGs with various surface textures to Cu substrate: none/control (a-b), chemically etched (c-d), and laser engraved (e-f). (a) Potential for base design of non-contact hydraulic TENG at 30 measurements/s (mV). (b) Current for base design of non-contact Hydraulic TENG at 30 measurements/s (mA). (c) Potential for etched design of non-contact hydraulic TENG at 32 measurements/s (mV). (d) current for etched design of non-contact hydraulic TENG at 30 measurements/s (mA). (e) potential for engraved design of non-contact hydraulic TENG at 30 measurements/s (mV). (f) Current for engraved design of non-Contact hydraulic TENG at 30 measurements/s (mA).

increased opportunity for the FEP to pull electrons off the substrate. Two distinct methods that offer a cheap, repeatable method to increase the surface area – chemical etching, as seen on the TENG in Fig. 1(a-b), and laser engraving, characterized by Fig. 2(a-b) – allowed for comparison of the factors, including output and applicability, for the TENG.

Results still showed oscillating data from an alternating current from spinning at 100-110 RPM. The average millivolts at the peaks for the base TENG design was -2.78 mV, -3.38 mV for the etched TENG design, and 21.41 for the engraved design (Fig. 3(a, c, e)). Due to the oscillations, the expected values were near zero. The f-tests showed statistical significance; the p-values were at 1.46E-32 and 0.

Since the etched Cu oxidized over the course of a month, the voltage values increased a thousand-fold, and the amperage decreased a thousand-fold. This can be seen where the averages for the peaks: 169.20 mV for the base TENG

design, 248.57 mV for the engraved TENG design, and 244619 mV for the etched TENG design. The outputs were therefore not directly comparable and were instead qualitatively compared for application potential.

As for the current, the average milliamps for the base design TENG were 0.35 mA, and 0.35 mA for the engraved TENG design, and 0.00035 for the etched TENG design (Fig. 3(b, d, f)). As a result of the discrepancy, the average amount of joules was calculated by multiplying the current and potential. As a result, 0.086 mJ/s were calculated to be produced by both the etched and engraved designs - a 45% increase as compared to the control.

Finally, regression was used to test the null hypothesis that the peaks are unpredictable in this data spread, where the r value should be approximately 0. Indeed, the R-value was at 0.0021/0.05/0.02 for the peak data values for the base/etched TENG designs. For the control and etched variables, there was an insignificant trendline, but for the engraved variable there was a slightly negative trendline that was significant (Fig. 4(a-b)).

With more time, more intricate details such as spacings and size could have been narrowed down. It was assumed that the voltage did not yet meet the threshold to power any low-powered sensor, yet because past data from the author produced an upwards for 1.5 V, that it could be assumed a low-powered sensor, when combined with a hydraulic, non-contact design that is more feasible than a rotating disk could power a sensor that requires no more than 1.5 V and 0.3 mA so long as the spacing between the triboelectric series was decreased to 1-2 mm, as gap distance between the substrate and polymer play a large role in overall output. Furthermore, an additional increase in output may be possible by altering the FEP polymer to increase its negative charge.

While previous research has taken an approach in maximizing the output in a lab, this triboelectric nanogenerator instead focuses on cheap and easily replicable methods by using cheaper methods to alter the substrate to increase its surface area without expensive equipment. Furthermore, with only one publicly available article by Zhang et. al (2020) on this type of TENG, hydraulic non-contact cylindrical, it expands on this niche in aims of expanding its perceived value.

The implications lie in hydraulic and sewage systems. For hydraulic systems, it becomes necessary to consider locations that provide the most mechanical energy from water, rather than decide where to place the system based on the local human population density. Many areas where hydraulic systems might be useful do not necessarily correlate with easy transportation for a mechanic to check every aspect of the system. Instead, the low-powered sensors powered by non-contact hydraulic TENGs can provide important data measurements - water pressure, humidity, potential, among others - that when processed can provide insight to whether the machine needs maintenance. For example, if the water pressure goes down a mechanic could be sent only for that day to fix that one specific piece of

Figure 4. Relation of voltage over time for peak data: A regression analysis. (a) Regression analysis for the laser engraved TENG. (b) Regression analysis for the chemically etched TENG.

equipment. TENGs use the already available energy resources that would otherwise be wasted, and overtime can sustain themselves in a way that batteries cannot. As for the sewage systems the idea is similar. If a TENG was placed say, every 30 feet of piping, any inhibition of free-flowing water would be reflected in the data collected by the low-powered sensors, and it could be narrowed, saving time for a minimally invasive alternative to fix the pipe based on which TENG picked up the change in water flow.

CONCLUSION

With a high voltage and low amperage, the triboelectric nanogenerator has proven itself capable of powering low-powered sensors, meaning the engineering goal was partially achieved.

However, this cylindrical design did not yet have enough current to power a low-powered sensor. Calculations show the capabilities to power a device and how it would work, but the voltage was lower than previous research by the author. This is likely due to the greater gap between the Cu strips and FEP - being 3 mm instead of under 2 mm. It is likely there is an inverse exponential function, where the extra gap led to less electron transfer. It is expected that an increase of 10x would result from decreasing the gap, which would produce enough energy to power a device, based on previous studies done by the researcher.

At first, while testing the data at a rate of 10 times a second, the data showed significance in the etched design producing higher voltage. Furthermore, it had a much higher frequency for peaks. While it is the better option for use in a triboelectric nanogenerator, the increase is somewhat marginal, at 18 mV increase. The consistency of the etched triboelectric nanogenerator is generally more valued. However, this sampling rate of this phase of testing does not represent the final conclusions due to the rate at which the testing was conducted, being insufficient due to aliasing.

Later, the relationship between surface area and power output was shown to have stronger support based on the second set of data collection. This is where the Cu metal with engraved designs from a laser was added. Furthermore, the tests were now 30 times a second, to measure the full oscillations in the data. Here, the energy output was nearly doubled from a combination of increased data measurements (that allowed for consistent measurements of the top of the peaks), as well as the increased surface area. Interestingly, after the etched Cu substrate was left exposed to open air on the TENG, it oxidized. After a month, when it was retested, the oxidation increased the resistance of the electrical circuit. While the voltage increased from 300 mV to 300,000 mV, the amperage decreased from 0.35 mA to 300 microamps. This means that in joules, the engraved Cu variable still outdid the etched variable, and in line with the etched metal's poor applicability over time, it can be concluded that the engraved Cu is the superior option for a TENG design meant to last on its own and exposed to the elements for prolonged periods of time. While not useful in application, future testing could take advantage of the oxidation to test DC current options for triboelectric nanogenerators without need for transformers, allowing for the expansion of techniques to allow direct power for TENGs, which almost exclusively produce fast pulses of oscillating data, as seen in this experiment.

Other traits achieved this year aid in the eventual application of the triboelectric nanogenerator. For one, it is frictionless - it can spin 100-110 RPM from a faucet. All the energy came from flowing water, showing that this design can be powered only by a renewable power source. Additionally, it does not lose voltage over time, trendlines were overall insignificant and therefore can be concluded that no factors were identified that could decrease efficiency over time. This triboelectric nanogenerator has the capabilities to last much longer if it was fully integrated into the water source.

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